

INGLIZ TILIDAGI MODAL FE'LLARDA AKSIOLOGIK BAHONING SHAKLLANISHI

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Annotatsiya

Annotatsiya. Ingliz tilidagi modal fe'llar epistemik (*must, might, may*) va deontik (*must, may, mustn't*) rejimlarda baholash mazmunini shakllantiradi. Epistemik shakllar ishonchlilik darajasini gradatsiyalab, bahoni qat'iy lashtiradi, yumshatadi yoki ochiq qoldiradi. Deontik shakllar esa majburiyat, ruxsat va taqiq orqali xatti-harakatning ijtimoiy me'yorlarga muvofiqligini belgilaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: *modal fe'llar, epistemik modallik, deontik modallik, aksiologik baholash, ishonchlilik darajasi, majburiyat, pragmatika, diskurs.*

Ingliz tilida modal fe'llar baholash mazmunini ifodalashda o'ziga xos xususiyatga ega. Modal fe'llar ikki – *epistemic* hamda *deontik* vazifalarda keladi.

Epistemik vazifasida kelganda so'zlovchi modal fe'llardan ishonchlilik darajasini ifodalash maqsadida foydalaniladi, unda yuqori ishonch sifatida *must*, past ishonch darajasini *might* hamda tahmini *may* modal fe'li orqali ifodalaniladi¹. Epistemik vazifasidagi modal fe'llar baholovchi struktura sifatida predmet, hodisaga nisbatan shaxsning *haqiqatan ham* yoki *ehtimol* tarzidagi ijobiy va salbiy bahosini shakllantiradi hamda tinglovchi ongida ushbu bahoni qat'iy lashtirish(*must*), yumshatish(*might*) yoki suhbatni ochiq qoldirish, ya'ni tahmin ustida mulohaza yuritish orqali aksiologik nuqtai nazarni boshqarishga xizmat qiladi. Masalan,

“An excellent point,” said Professor Dumbledore. “My own brother, Aberforth, was prosecuted for practicing inappropriate charms on a goat. It was all over the papers, but did Aberforth hide? No, he did not! He held his head high and went about his business as usual! Of course, I’m not entirely sure he can read, so that may not have been bravery. . . .”(J.K.Rowling “Harry Potter”)

Quyida keltirilgan matnda *I’m not entirely sure* iborasida modal fe'l ishtirok etmagan bo'lsa-da, epistemic vazifasida kelgan ehtimollik ma'nosi ta'kidlangan.. *May not have been bravery* tarkibidagi *may* fe'li orqali esa so'zlovchi jasorat sifatini qat'iy tasdiqlamaydi, balki bu xususiyatning mavjudligi to'g'risida tahmin bildiradi. Bunda u tinglovchiga Aberforth harakatini ijobiy baholashdan oldin yana o'ylab ko'rishni taklif qiladi, aksiologik bahoni kengaytiradi. Ya'ni *He held his head high* gapi ijobiy tarzda qahramonlikni ifodalasa, *may not have been bravery* esa shu ijobiy bahoni biroz yumshatirib, tinglovchida qarama qarshi munosabatni yuzaga kelishiga xizmat qilmoqda.

Modal fe'llarning deontik modallik vazifasida ijtimoiy me'yorlar, majburiyat, taqiq ko'rsatiladi². Bu esa ularning aksiologik leksik birlik sifatida biror bir shaxsning xatti-harakatini ijtimoiy me'yorga muvofiq yoki nomuvofiqligini aniqlashga xizmat qiladi. Xususan, unda *majburiyat*(*you must...*), *ruxsat*(*you may...*) hamda *taqiq*(*you mustn't...*) kabi munosabatlar aks etadi. Masalan,

“Two things at once impressed themselves on Mr. Lorry, as important above all others; the first, that this must be kept secret from Lucie; the second, that it must be kept secret from all who knew him. In conjunction with Miss Pross, he took immediate steps towards the latter precaution, by giving out that the Doctor was not well, and required a few days of complete rest.”(Ch.Dickens “A tale of two cities”)

¹ Halliday M.A., Christian M.I. Halliday's Introduction to Functional Grammar. – Routledge, 2013. – P. 172-193.

² Halliday M.A., Christian M.I. Halliday's Introduction to Functional Grammar. – Routledge, 2013. – P. 172-193.

Matndagi *must* modal fe'li aksiologik leksik birlik sifatida sirni oshkor qilmaslik majburiyati kabi munosabatini ifodalaydi. Matnda sirni oshkor qilmaslik eng muhim ijtimoiy jarayon sifatida *must* yordamida tasvirlanib, voqeagadramatik tus beradi. Ushbu majburiyatni ikkinchi marotaba ta'kidlash sirni himoya qilish ma'suliyatini yanada mustahkamlaydi.

Demak, modal fe'llar informativ vositadan tashqari, diskursda aksiologik yo'nalishni boshqaruvchi pragmatik indikator hisoblanadi. Epistemik modal birliklar tinglovchi ongida ijobiy/salbiy baho intensivligini nozik sozlaydi. Deontik modal birliklar esa normativ bosimni kuchaytirib, ijtimoiy qadriyatlar doirasini aniq belgilaydi.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Halliday M.A., Christian M.I. Halliday's Introduction to Functional Grammar. – Routledge, 2013. – P. 172-193.